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**DIGITAL MODELS OF ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING OF
PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS IN
BLENDED LEARNING CONDITIONS (EXPERIENCE OF THE PRC)**

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Abstract. The thesis analyzes digital models for assessing and monitoring physical activity of higher education students in blended learning in the field of physical education using the example of the People's Republic of China. A pedagogically appropriate approach is justified, according to which digital data is considered as a tool for formative assessment and support of pedagogical decisions, and not as an autonomous control mechanism. It is shown that the effectiveness of digital models is determined by their consistency with didactic logic, the role of the teacher in interpreting data, as well as compliance with the principles of safety, ethics and equal access.

Keywords: digital assessment, physical education, blended learning, higher education.

Анотація. У тезах проаналізовано цифрові моделі оцінювання та моніторингу фізичної активності здобувачів вищої освіти в умовах змішаного навчання у галузі фізичної культури на прикладі Китайської Народної Республіки. Обґрунтовано педагогічно доцільний підхід, відповідно до якого цифрові дані розглядаються як інструмент формувального оцінювання та підтримки педагогічних рішень, а не як автономний механізм контролю. Показано, що ефективність цифрових моделей визначається їх узгодженістю з дидактичною логікою, роллю викладача в інтерпретації даних, а також дотриманням принципів безпеки, етичності та рівного доступу.

Ключові слова: цифрове оцінювання, фізична культура, змішане навчання, вища освіта.

The organization of the educational process of higher education students in the field of physical education in the context of digitalization increasingly depends on how the control of motor activity, assessment of learning outcomes and monitoring of physical activity are combined in the training. Unlike many other educational fields, physical education is characterized by the dominance of “embodied” learning: mastering the technique of movements, developing physical qualities, safe dosage of load and the formation of self-regulation skills are not additional, but system-forming components of the educational result. That is why digital technologies, which in other

disciplines mostly enhance content management or communication, in physical culture claim a more complex function - to indirectly influence the quality of pedagogical decisions through data, measurements, analytics and feedback mechanisms. In the context of the PRC, this issue takes on particular importance, since the digital transformation of education is conceptualized through the framework of “smart education”, which involves not only digital resources, but also the formation of holistic ecosystems in which data supports educational and management processes [1]. At the same time, the research interest in digital tools in physical education is accompanied by discussions about the pedagogical correctness of “data-driven” approaches: quantitative indicators of activity can create the illusion of objectivity and progress, but without pedagogical interpretation they can simplify learning to track metrics, without taking into account context, safety, motivation and individual limitations [4]. These contradictions lead to a key scientific task: to find out which digital models of assessment and monitoring are pedagogically justified for blended learning in physical education in higher education institutions in the PRC and what conditions ensure their effectiveness.

Modern systematic reviews record a significant expansion of the spectrum of digital solutions in physical education - from video analysis of equipment and mobile applications to complexes with sensory devices and algorithmic feedback tools. At the same time, it is emphasized that the effectiveness of “digital-intelligent technologies” in physical culture cannot be reduced to technical characteristics: the decisive factors are pedagogical coherence with the learning objectives and the role of human actors (teacher and learner) in explaining data and transforming them into educational action [4]. Accordingly, the issue of assessment and monitoring goes beyond the “instrumental” approach and is considered as part of didactic design.

In the broader educational discourse of “smart education”, it is emphasized that digital transformation inevitably raises issues of equality of access, transparency of assessment, ethical use of data, and alignment of digital mechanisms with the goals of human and social development [3]. For the PRC, attempts to systematize the transformation of education at the level of institutional reports and indicators, which include both digital maturity measurements, infrastructure development, and

management mechanisms to support innovation [1], are indicative. The national scientific discourse also emphasizes the multidimensionality of the challenges of modernizing education in the PRC in the 21st century, including issues of quality, system adaptability, and the need to combine innovation with cultural and value orientations [2]. Taken together, these approaches allow us to argue that digital models of assessment and monitoring in physical education should be analyzed as an element of organizing the educational process – both pedagogical and managerial.

In blended learning in physical education, assessment and monitoring take on a dual function. On the one hand, they provide a final record of results (achievement of standards, development of technique, compliance with program requirements). On the other hand, they support the formative logic: they help the learner adjust behavior, control the workload, be aware of their own progress, and learn self-regulation. In the digital environment, these two functions are often mixed, which creates the risk of methodological ambiguity when the same digital indicator is used both as “data for learning” and as “data for assessment,” and therefore changes the learner’s motivation, increases anxiety, or provokes formal behavior.

A pedagogically sound model of digital assessment in physical education can be described as a system in which digital data does not replace the teacher’s professional judgment, but structures it, increases the evidence base, and increases the regularity of feedback. In such a model, it is appropriate to distinguish at least three analytical levels. The first level is related to data on the volume and rhythm of activity: frequency of training sessions, duration, intensity, steps, heart rate zones, etc. The second level concerns the quality of movement performance and technique, which can be assessed through video recordings, checklists, the teacher’s expert scale and/or digital error visualization tools. The third level reflects the subjective state of the learner well-being, recovery, sense of load that is, indicators without which assessment loses its safety dimension. It is the combination of these levels that allows us to avoid reducing learning to the “chasing of metrics”, which is typical of a purely quantitative approach [4].

In the PRC practices focused on “smart education”, digital solutions are often implemented in the form of platform ecosystems, where LMS is combined with

mobile services, analytical panels, video content libraries and feedback tools. However, the pedagogical value of such ecosystems is not determined by their complexity, but by how transparently they are linked to the objectives of the educational program and how they support informed management decisions on the quality of teaching [1]. In this sense, digital assessment and monitoring models can act as a “bridge” between the level of individual learning and the level of institutional quality: data on the regularity of participation, group progress, typical errors in technique or risk zones of overload become the basis for the correction of training modules and methodologies.

At the same time, the peculiarity of physical education is that any digital assessment mechanism actually intervenes in the behavior of the learner. If the digital system emphasizes only the final result, learners may choose “demonstration strategies” instead of development strategies: striving to quickly increase the indicator, ignoring technique and safety, or looking for ways to “bypass” the measurement. If assessment is structured as formative, and digital metrics are explained in an educational context, they can become a tool for self-regulation and intrinsic motivation. Here, the role of the teacher as an interpreter is fundamentally important: he must transform data into pedagogical meanings - explain what exactly the change in the indicator means, how it is related to movement technique, recovery and educational goal, as well as why in a certain situation “less is better, but safer”.

In the global dimension, ethical requirements are imposed on digital assessment and monitoring related to privacy, transparency of algorithms and non-discrimination. Data on physical activity and health are sensitive, and therefore their collection and use require clear rules of access and consent, data minimization, justification of pedagogical necessity and prevention of situations where digital indicators become a source of stigmatization or informal pressure [3]. In blended learning, these risks are exacerbated by the blurring of boundaries between academic and extracurricular activities: if the system “sees” activity outside of classes, the question arises where educational control ends and the student’s private space begins.

Given this, a pedagogically correct model of digital assessment in physical education in higher education institutions in the PRC should be built on the principle

of limited and targeted instrumentalization of data. Digital indicators should be used as an evidentiary basis for formative feedback and as an auxiliary component of summative assessment, but with clearly defined boundaries for their use. It is also important to ensure equality of access: if some students do not have wearable devices or stable Internet access, assessment cannot be completely “tied” to such tools; instead, there should be alternative procedures for recording activity and progress. In a broader perspective, these conditions are consistent with the approach to education reform in the PRC, which emphasizes the need to combine innovation with systemic mechanisms for the quality and manageability of educational change [1; 2].

Digital models of assessment and monitoring in blended learning in physical education in higher education institutions in the PRC should be considered as a tool for pedagogical management of educational activities, rather than as a mechanism for automated replacement of teaching judgment. Their effectiveness is determined by the extent to which data is integrated into the didactic logic of the module, the extent to which they support the safety and self-regulation of the learner, and the extent to which the boundaries of their use are transparently defined. Systematic reviews confirm that the technological effect in physical education is manifested when digital solutions are consistent with the nature of “embodied” learning and complement the interaction of the teacher and the learner, rather than replacing it [4].

A promising direction for further research is the empirical verification of the described model on a sample of higher education institutions in the PRC with a comparative analysis: do learning outcomes and the stability of students’ participation in physical education modules increase; how motivation and attitudes towards assessment change; what risks arise in data collection practices; and what organizational configurations (combination of platforms, assessment procedures, and feedback forms) are most pedagogically justified in blended learning settings.

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